

Tailoring the topological surface states in $\text{Bi}_{1.9}\text{Sb}_{0.1}\text{Se}_3$ by 140 keV proton irradiation

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Abstract

Three-dimensional (3D) topological insulators (TI) are a new class of materials with two-dimensional (2D) conducting Dirac surface states (SS) that host highly mobile and spin-polarized Dirac fermions. Here we report the ion irradiation induced changes in the TI properties. Single crystals of $\text{Bi}_{1.9}\text{Sb}_{0.1}\text{Se}_3$ were irradiated with 140 keV proton beam with different ion fluences of 10^{14} , 10^{16} , and 10^{17} ions/cm². The magnetotransport studies on the pristine and proton irradiated $\text{Bi}_{1.9}\text{Sb}_{0.1}\text{Se}_3$ sample shows Shubnikov-de Haas (SdH) oscillation and from Lifshitz-Kosovitch (LK) analysis, they showed SS characteristics with Berry phase factor $\beta \sim 0.6$. However, the frequency of the oscillation decreases systematically from 156 T for the pristine sample to 136 T in irradiated sample. From Onsager relation, it depicts that E_F is shifted downward toward the Dirac point (DP). Bulk carrier density deduced from the Hall data shows a non-monotonic behavior. Whereas, the surface carrier density deduced from the SdH fit exhibits a systematic decrease due to the reduction in the area of the 2D Dirac surface states. Proton beam induced strain in the sample and its effect on the electronic band structure is believed to shift the Fermi level towards DP. TEM and Raman scattering studies show the existence of compressive strain in the system.

Keywords: **Topological insulators, Ion beam irradiation, Magnetotransport.**